
AI governance around the world

Country profile: India

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About The Alan Turing Institute

The Alan Turing Institute is the UK's national institute for data science and artificial intelligence.

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About the project

Introduction

The international AI governance landscape continues to evolve as jurisdictions around the world balance the need to navigate increased competition with earlier commitments to advancing international alignment and cooperation on AI governance and safety. Many jurisdictions have recognised the strategic implications of AI, both for economic prosperity and national security, and accelerated investment in domestic AI infrastructure has begun to engender a more competitive international environment. However, the role of international trade and global cooperation remains crucial in realising the economic benefits of AI while effectively managing the technology's risks.

As high-level AI principles are translated into concrete policies and distinct regulatory frameworks, jurisdictions are managing the tensions between competitive and cooperative priorities. Meaningful progress towards effective international AI governance will require a clear and detailed understanding of how different countries are approaching AI governance in practice. Tracking primary source policy initiatives over the past decade, the *AI governance around the world* project sheds light on shifting national priorities on AI, dynamics of cooperation and competition, and potential areas of international alignment.

Project aims

The *AI governance around the world* project seeks to map this evolving landscape through a series of country profiles based on a consistent framework. Each profile provides a descriptive overview of a jurisdiction's approach to AI regulation and standardisation, highlighting the high-level aims and principles, definitions of relevant technologies, key policy initiatives and the main features of the respective standardisation systems. Drawing exclusively on primary sources, the country profiles analyse legal and policy instruments, national strategies, standardisation initiatives, and public investments that reflect the varied and evolving approaches that different jurisdictions are taking to AI governance.

This series offers a foundation for comparative analysis and future work on global regulatory interoperability without commenting on the efficacy of the specific governance models being adopted at the jurisdictional level. As more profiles are developed, the project aims to contribute to international understanding of where alignment is emerging and where deeper coordination may be needed.

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Executive summary

India's government is principally committed to advancing the domestic adoption of AI technologies, with stated interests in stimulating economic growth and bringing about positive social impact. Strategic policy documents also reflect a strong interest in improving India's AI infrastructure and workforce. AI technologies are increasingly integral to the delivery of public services in India, including the country's national biometric identity system. Several state governments have also begun to use AI in areas like policing, agriculture, transport, and education.

The Government of India has not proposed comprehensive AI-related legislation, and governance considerations are generally not given systematic attention in strategic policy documents. The government has nonetheless gradually begun to introduce hard measures—akin to administrative acts or directives—that rely on existing IT laws to set limits on the behaviours of AI platforms. India has also participated in international governance initiatives and is a signatory to the Bletchley and Seoul declarations, signalling its interest in global coordination on AI governance.

Indian institutions are actively monitoring opportunities for alignment with international AI standardisation efforts, primarily from the view that standards will facilitate public trust, encourage adoption, and improve performance in AI systems aiding in the delivery of public services.

Key policy initiatives

- Mar 2018** **Artificial Intelligence Task Force Report**
Government report outlining opportunities for India's AI ecosystem
- Jun 2018** **National AI Strategy**
National AI Strategy published by NITI Aayog, the government's public policy think tank
- Jul 2019** **MEITY committee reports**
Four-part series analysing India's AI ecosystem, published by Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology
- Feb 2021** **Information Technology Rules**
Voluntary framework defining values for responsible AI (updated 2023)
- 2021–22** **Responsible #AIForAll**
Publication series outlining considerations for responsible AI, published by NITI Aayog
- Aug 2023** **Digital Personal Data Protection Act**
Detailed rules for the collection, processing, and maintenance of personal data in India
- Mar 2024** **MEITY due diligence advisory**
Policy mandating due diligence from companies developing or using AI systems that could create or disseminate harmful content

Regulatory approach to AI

High-level aims and principles

Since at least 2017, the Indian government has indicated a clear focus on enriching the nation's AI ecosystem, which it states will contribute to improving social and economic conditions within the country and advancing India's global position in the AI economy.¹ Many strategic policy documents emphasise sectoral opportunities for AI adoption and growth, indicating a strongly vertical approach to leveraging AI systems for social and economic benefit. The government has also invested in programmes to support industrial, infrastructural, and training activities it sees as critical to expand its domestic AI ecosystem.

Many public bodies in India have expressed concerns about the potential for increased legislation to impede innovation, and so far no AI-specific legislation has been proposed. In recent years, however, the Government of India—principally via its Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MEITY)—has indicated its intent to rely on existing IT laws to govern AI risks, chiefly by issuing an “advisory” that requires intermediaries and platforms using AI technologies to conduct “due diligence” to obtain government permission before deploying certain systems.²

Finally, AI technologies are playing an increasingly important role in enabling the delivery of public services in India, including the country's national biometric identity system.

Definitions of relevant technologies

In early policy documents, the Indian government took a mixed approach to defining AI and related terms in policy documents and other materials: some references to artificial intelligence did not explicitly define the term, while others characterised AI in grand

¹ 'National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence #AIFORALL Discussion Paper' (NITI Aayog, June 2018), 5, <https://indiaai.gov.in/documents/pdf/NationalStrategy-for-AI-Discussion-Paper.pdf>.

² 'Due diligence by Intermediaries / Platforms under the Information Technology Act, 2000 and the Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021' (Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, Cyber Law and Data Governance Group, 2024), <https://www.meity.gov.in/static/uploads/2024/02/9f6e99572739a3024c9cdaec53a0a0ef.pdf>.

terms, employing analogies to human cognitive capacities. More recent publications indicate recognition of definitions developed by key international bodies.

In India's 2018 National AI Strategy, the National Institute for Transforming India (NITI Aayog³), a government think tank, defined AI anthropomorphically as “a constellation of technologies that enable machines to act with higher levels of intelligence and emulate the human capabilities of sense, comprehend and act (sic)”.⁴ Computer vision, audio processing, and natural language processing were given as examples of technologies that can “actively” emulate human perceptual and cognitive faculties, and AI-based decision systems are described as “undertak[ing],” rather than enabling humans to undertake, “actions in the physical world”.⁵

Committees of the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology were more reserved in their characterisation of AI in an influential series of reports published in 2019. One report explicitly dismissed the notion that machines could ‘think’ like humans, arguing that this industry “promise” has “never materialized”.⁶ Nevertheless, while the reports defined some terms when contextually appropriate—like ‘data’, ‘platform’, and ‘machine learning’—none provided an explicit definition of AI, instead giving examples of AI systems and their components where relevant.

More recently, a 2023 report from the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI) includes comments on the challenges associated with defining AI and sources indicative definitions from other normative references, including NITI Aayog's as well as those developed by key international bodies like the OECD and the EU. Definitions of AI from SDOs, including ITU, ETSI, and the terminology standard ISO/IEC 22989:2022, are also cited.

Key policy initiatives

Publications from several national bodies—the Ministry of Commerce and Industry's AI task force (AITF), the National Institute for Transforming India (NITI Aayog), the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MEITY), the Department of

³ Formed by the Government of India in 2015, NITI Aayog—which literally translates to ‘Policy Commission’—is responsible for driving and publicising Indian policy research, initiatives, and strategies.

⁴ ‘National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence #AIFORALL Discussion Paper’, 12.

⁵ ‘National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence #AIFORALL Discussion Paper’, 12.

⁶ ‘Report of Committee C on Mapping Technological Capabilities, Key Policy Enablers Required Across Sectors, Skilling and Re-Skilling, R&D’ (Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, July 2019), 6, https://www.meity.gov.in/writereaddata/files/Committees_C-Report-on_RnD.pdf.

Telecommunications (DoT), and the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI)—are indicative of cross-governmental interest in addressing the risks and opportunities of AI adoption.

Key among these publications are NITI Aayog’s Responsible #AIforAll series, which introduces the government’s approach to managing AI-related social and ethical concerns but has yet to materialise in policy, and a series of reports developed by committees MEITY established to identify national needs for AI R&D and governance. Together, these documents reflect the Indian government’s interest in facilitating adoption of AI to bring social and economic benefit in key sectors, as well as the government’s hesitancy when it comes to imposing formal rules.

The government has also established initiatives and resource platforms aimed at strengthening its domestic or “indigenous” AI ecosystem. An important example is the IndiaAI mission, a strategic initiative accompanied by comprehensive online platform for news, initiatives, opportunities, and research related to India’s AI ecosystem.⁷ Although lacking explicitly central coordination, these initiatives—along with the disparate activities and publications of several government departments—reflect a fairly cohesive set of priorities for the future of AI in India.

Finally, central and state governments have embraced using AI to deliver policy objectives and public services. Numerous state governments have commissioned and deployed AI systems across a range of governance functions.

Horizontal initiatives

Strategies, frameworks, and reports

Report of the AITF

In 2017, the Ministry of Commerce and Industry created a task force with the intent to study how to “leverage AI for economic benefits” and lay the foundations for the “creation of [a] legal and policy framework to accelerate deployment of AI technologies.”⁸ The AITF’s report, published in 2018, outlines a broad vision for the use of AI in India. It provides detailed analyses of strategic sectors—like agriculture, utility provision, education, and, crucially, national security—and necessary “enablers”—including influencing social attitudes, broadening data literacy, and pursuing international

⁷ ‘INDIAai | Pillars,’ Government of India, <https://indiaai.gov.in/>.

⁸ ‘Artificial Intelligence Task Force,’ Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India, <https://www.aif.org.in/>.

regulatory alignment—for AI adoption, alongside a two-page overview of considerations for ensuring responsible use.⁹

The AITF Report represents one of the earliest comprehensive attempts by India's government to lay out a vision for the future of AI in India. It shares common features with much of the work that has followed it, including emphases on sectoral adoption and the need to strengthen domestic capacity, alongside separate consideration of ethical and societal risks.

National AI Strategy (#AIForAll)

India's National AI Strategy, released by NITI Aayog in 2018 and promoted under the tagline #AIForAll, exemplifies the country's pro-innovation attitude. The Strategy identifies key sectors for AI adoption and provides recommendations for education and workforce training, areas of research, and opportunities for government intervention.¹⁰

MEITY committee reports

The Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MEITY), via its Emerging Technologies division, has been influential in India's AI policy planning. In 2017, MEITY announced it had established four committees composed of technical experts from academia and industry. Each committee was tasked with providing guidance for a specific set of issues related to the advancement of India's AI ecosystem. The resulting four-part framework covers proposals related to data infrastructure (Committee A), sectoral AI adoption (Committee B), research and workforce capacity (Committee C), and governance issues, including cybersecurity, privacy, and ethics (Committee D).

The MEITY committee reports analyse India's national needs in key areas and provide recommendations, rather than making specific directives. Nevertheless, many of these recommendations have ultimately—if perhaps not directly—materialised in concrete policy initiatives. For example, in its 2019 report on Platforms and Data in Artificial Intelligence, Committee A advocated for greater availability, interoperability, and quality in AI training data, encouraging an investment of INR 100 crore (nearly GBP 10 million)¹¹; today, the Indian government devotes resources to providing open data

⁹ 'Report of The Artificial Intelligence Task Force' (AITF, 2018), https://dpiit.gov.in/sites/default/files/Report_of_Task_Force_on_ArtificialIntelligence_20March2018_2.pdf.

¹⁰ 'National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence #AIFORALL Discussion Paper'.

¹¹ 'Report of Committee A on Platforms and Data in Artificial Intelligence', 11–12.

platforms for AI developers within the country who may lack the resources to procure data themselves.

Committee C tackled workforce training needs in its report, calling for the expansion of training opportunities in complex technical fields, the cultivation of interdisciplinary expertise to meet AI governance needs, and the expansion of research and educational capabilities beyond a handful of elite technical institutions.¹² Today, the country has seen government interest in expanding the country's research and educational capacity.¹³

Like the AITF report and the NITI Aayog publication series, the MEITY committee reports advocate sectoral investment and sectoral governance. Committee B's report identifies opportunities for AI adoption in 17 sectors across India's economy (e.g., "optimising pesticide consumption" within agriculture¹⁴ and "traffic control and monitoring" within transportation¹⁵), although it does not discuss potential risks associated with the use of AI in these contexts. And in its report covering governance considerations, Committee D argues that "horizontal regulations on AI technologies would limit innovation" while "a sectoral approach to regulating AI would allow for greater flexibility".¹⁶ The report also repeatedly suggests that existing laws related to discrimination, privacy, data protection, and intellectual property may impose "constraints which hamper responsible use of AI", arguing that "excessive regulations" could "hinder the growth of the technology".¹⁷

Responsible #AIForAll

After the publication of the National AI Strategy in 2018, NITI Aayog released three documents in a series titled Responsible #AIForAll, which expands on the Strategy with specific emphasis on encouraging the responsible adoption of AI across sectors. The Responsible AI series frames its approach in terms of the "considerations" that must be taken into account in order to mitigate negative impacts of AI systems. These fall into two broad categories: "systems considerations," which can protect against negative

¹² 'Report of Committee C on Mapping Technological Capabilities, Key Policy Enablers Required Across Sectors, Skilling and Re-Skilling, R&D', 21–24.

¹³ 'AI Centres of Excellence' (Ministry of Education, 18 November 2023), https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/Call-for-Proposal.pdf.

¹⁴ 'Report of Committee B on Leveraging AI for Identifying National Missions in Key Sectors', 8.

¹⁵ 'Report of Committee B on Leveraging AI for Identifying National Missions in Key Sectors', 12.

¹⁶ 'Report of Committee D on Cyber Security, Safety, Legal and Ethical Issues', 36.

¹⁷ 'Report of Committee D on Cyber Security, Safety, Legal and Ethical Issues', 37.

impacts to individuals, such as the subjects of AI-based decisions, and “societal considerations,” which can mitigate wider risks.¹⁸

Report on AI Governance Guidelines Development

In 2025, MEITY released a report analysing India’s domestic capacity for AI governance. The report, authored by a multi-stakeholder advisory group convened by India’s Principal Scientific Advisor, advocates a “coordinated, whole-of-government approach to ensure effective compliance and enforcement as India’s AI landscape continues to evolve.” It also provides recommendations to pursue further study, implement voluntary governance mechanisms across government, and consider strengthening legal, regulatory, and technical capacity for AI.

Initiatives and resources

IndiaAI mission

In addition to publishing its committee reports in 2019, MEITY was instrumental in establishing India’s first national AI resource platform, IndiaAI, in 2020. With an expansive “mission” to “establish a comprehensive ecosystem catalysing innovation...across the public and private sectors,” the IndiaAI programme received INR 10,370 crore (around GBP 890 million) in government funding in 2024.¹⁹

Today, IndiaAI’s online platform maintains a range of resources for the Indian AI ecosystem, including informational resources (news, research reports, case studies, e-learning modules) and networking resources (events, companies, funding resources), as well as infrastructure resources and projects for AI developers (curated datasets, expanded affordable compute, “indigenous” foundation model development). IndiaAI also collects AI-related news in five strategic sectors (healthcare, finance, agriculture, cybersecurity, and education), and tracks progress on international AI policy.

Laws and policies

Information Technology Act (2000)

¹⁸ ‘Cabinet Approves Ambitious IndiaAI Mission to Strengthen the AI Innovation Ecosystem,’ Government of India Press Information Bureau, 7 March 2024, <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleaselframePage.aspx?PRID=2012357>.

¹⁹ ‘Report on AI Governance Guidelines Development’ (Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, December 2025), <https://indiaai.s3.ap-south-1.amazonaws.com/docs/subcommittee-report-dec26.pdf>.

India's IT Act came into force on 17 October 2000, formally recognising means of electronic communication while defining a range of penalties for acts considered "cybercrime". Later amended to address issues relating to pornography and terrorism, the IT Act contains some provisions that might be applicable to the governance of AI technologies, including prohibitions on breaches of privacy (§72).²⁰ However, the Act is mainly aimed at regulating electronic records, signatures, and transactions, and would likely require overhaul to be suited to address many AI-specific considerations.

Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021

Published in 2021 and updated in June 2023, the Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code is an official government publication with full legal force that requires "publishers" of digital content and relevant "intermediaries" to perform due diligence to avoid the dissemination of harmful, deceptive, fraudulent, or malicious content. Focused on social media and online gaming providers, the Guidelines include transparency requirements for companies and grant relevant authorities permission to inquire about potential wrongdoing detected. While "non-observance" is said to be punishable "under any law," no specific penalties are outlined.²¹

The policy does not specifically apply to AI, but includes references to relevant technologies in ways that suggest scope for applicable enforcement. Deepfakes ("artificially morphed images of...individual[s]"²²) are explicitly identified as prohibited content, for instance. In another instance, it is noted that the transmission of harmful content without explicitly applying forms of "automated or algorithmic editorial control"²³ (e.g., via an internet service provider) will not amount to a violation. Furthermore, this policy was expanded upon by MEITY in 2024 to elaborate specific due diligence requirements for intermediaries and platforms providing AI-enabled services.

Digital India Bill

Proposed by MEITY in 2023, the Digital India Bill (DIB), a draft piece of legislation intended to replace India's IT Act 2000, could have implications for the development and deployment of AI systems within the country. If passed, the DIB would set out

²⁰ The Information Technology Act, 2000 (Act 21 of 2000), https://www.meity.gov.in/static/uploads/2024/03/ITbill_2000.pdf.

²¹ 'The Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021', <https://www.meity.gov.in/static/uploads/2024/02/Information-Technology-Intermediary-Guidelines-and-Digital-Media-Ethics-Code-Rules-2021-updated-06.04.2023-.pdf>, Part II, 7.

²² 'The Information Technology Rules, 2021', Part II, 3. (2) (b)

²³ 'The Information Technology Rules, 2021', Part II, 3. (1) (e)

comprehensive new rules for engagement on the internet, including the “regulation of hi-risk AI systems through [a] legal, institutional quality testing framework”.²⁴

Digital Personal Data Protection Act (2023)

Originally proposed in 2022 by MEITY, the Digital Personal Data Protection Act—which the Parliament of India passed in 2023—sets out detailed rules for the collection, maintenance, and processing of personal data in India. The Act does not specifically cover artificial intelligence, but the formalisation of data protection rules in India is nevertheless likely to hold implications for the development and deployment of AI systems within the country in future.²⁵

Due diligence by Intermediaries / Platforms under the Information Technology Act, 2000 and Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021

This advisory was issued on 15 March 2024, superseding a version MEITY had issued two weeks earlier. Arguing that “intermediaries and platforms are often negligent in undertaking due-diligence obligations outlined” under the IT Act 2000 and the IT Rules 2021, MEITY states it is issuing an advisory to reiterate and expand upon existing provisions.²⁶

MEITY’s 2024 advisory explicitly prohibits the development or use of AI technologies that can disseminate unlawful content, perpetuate bias, threaten “the integrity of the electoral process,” or use “under-tested” or “unreliable” AI foundation models. It also includes requirements for AI companies to undertake “due diligence” to prevent these outcomes, for example by watermarking generated content that “may be used potentially as misinformation or deepfake.” Companies are further required to update user agreements to reflect these rules, and are advised that non-compliance could be prosecuted under the IT Act 2000.²⁷

²⁴ Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, ‘Proposed Digital India Act, 2023’, https://www.meity.gov.in/writereaddata/files/DIA_Presentation%2009.03.2023%20Final.pdf.

²⁵ ‘Digital Personal Data Protection Act’ (2023), <https://www.meity.gov.in/writereaddata/files/Digital%20Personal%20Data%20Protection%20Act%202023.pdf>.

²⁶ ‘Due diligence by Intermediaries / Platforms under the Information Technology Act, 2000 and the Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021’ (Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, Cyber Law and Data Governance Group, 2024), <https://www.meity.gov.in/static/uploads/2024/02/9f6e99572739a3024c9cdaec53a0a0ef.pdf>.

²⁷ ‘Due diligence by Intermediaries / Platforms under the Information Technology Act, 2000 and the Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021’ (Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, Cyber Law and Data Governance Group, 2024), <https://www.meity.gov.in/static/uploads/2024/02/9f6e99572739a3024c9cdaec53a0a0ef.pdf>.

Vertical initiatives

So far, the Indian government has not proposed any vertical AI legislation, instead opting to explore ways the government can use AI for social and economic benefit. Many of its policy documents are devoted to outlining sectoral opportunities for AI adoption, and many state governments have also begun to make use of AI systems to deliver public services.

Reporting for Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) applications and systems offered and used by market intermediaries

In 2019, the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) issued a circular on reporting requirements for AI and machine learning applications used to “facilitate investment and training”, to provide investment advice, or to support compliance. This circular requires relevant financial institutions using AI systems in these ways to report to SEBI on a quarterly basis on the nature of use and the implemented safeguards.²⁸

Ethical Guidelines for Application of Artificial Intelligence in Biomedical Research and Healthcare

Developed by the Indian Council of Medical Research, a Government-owned biomedical research body, the “Ethical Guidelines for Application of Artificial Intelligence in Biomedical Research and Healthcare” sets out a set of nonbinding guiding principles for the development and deployment of AI technologies across various relevant applications in the healthcare sector, including diagnostics, drug discovery, and clinical care.²⁹

Leveraging Artificial Intelligence and Big Data in the Telecommunications Sector

In July 2023, the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI) released a set of recommendations on “Leveraging Artificial Intelligence and Big Data in the

²⁸ ‘Reporting for Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) applications and systems offered and used by market intermediaries’ (Securities and Exchange Board of India, 4 January 2019), https://www.sebi.gov.in/legal/circulars/jan-2019/reporting-for-artificial-intelligence-ai-and-machine-learning-ml-applications-and-systems-offered-and-used-by-market-intermediaries_41546.html.

²⁹ ‘Ethical Guidelines for Application of Artificial Intelligence in Biomedical Research and Healthcare’ (Indian Council of Medical Research, 2023), https://main.icmr.nic.in/sites/default/files/upload_documents/Ethical_Guidelines_AI_Healthcare_2023.pdf.

Telecommunications Sector”.³⁰ The document surveys key international regulatory outputs, outlines AI-related risks, and identifies important “enablers” for AI adoption in telecommunications, including the development of targeted infrastructure, the introduction of accreditation mechanisms, and the adoption of privacy-enhancing technologies. TRAI’s most important, and most prominent, recommendation is for the Indian government to begin developing targeted AI regulation.

AI Centres of Excellence

In November 2023, the Government of India agreed to allocate INR 99 crore (more than GBP 93 million) over a period of five years to the establishment of three national AI centres of excellence (COEs)³¹, an initiative originally recommended in 2017 by the Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade.³² The original announcement explained that these COEs would each be housed at a top university within the country and dedicated to addressing challenges in a key sector: 1) Agriculture, 2) Health, and 3) Sustainable Cities.³³

IP Saarthi Chatbot

Developed by the Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade, which sits within the Ministry of Commerce & Industry, the IP Saarthi Chatbot was designed to assist users in “navigating the IP registration process” by facilitating trademark searches using natural language processing.³⁴

Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI)

In 2016, the Government of India first launched what is now the world’s largest biometric identity system, which provides Indian residents with a 12-digit identity number associated with unique biometric and demographic information. Already leveraging conventional machine learning techniques to match individuals’ biometric information with government records, the Aadhaar system, managed by the Unique Identification Authority of India, has rolled out additional AI-based features in recent years, including

³⁰ ‘Leveraging Artificial Intelligence and Big Data in Telecommunication Sector’ (Telecom Regulatory Authority of India, 20 July 2023), https://www.trai.gov.in/sites/default/files/Recommendation_20072023_0.pdf.

³¹ ‘AI Centres of Excellence’ (Ministry of Education, 18 November 2023), https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/Call-for-Proposal.pdf.

³² ‘Report of the Artificial Intelligence Task Force’ (Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade, 20 March 2018), <https://dpiit.gov.in/whats-new/report-task-force-artificial-intelligence>.

³³ ‘AI Centres of Excellence’.

³⁴ ‘Union Minister Piyush Goyal unveils AI and ML-based Trademark Search Technology, IP Saarthi Chatbot,’ IndiaAI, 20 September 2024, <https://indiaai.gov.in/article/union-minister-piyush-goyal-unveils-ai-and-ml-based-trademark-search-technology-ip-saarthi-chatbot>.

a chatbot trained to handle user inquiries and complaints³⁵ and a voice-based interaction service to support fraud detection.³⁶

State government uses of AI

Many state governments in India have been integrating AI solutions into the provision of public services like education and state governance.³⁷ This is no new trend: IndiaAI, which tracks the initiatives of Central Ministries and State Governments, contains reports dating back to at least 2020.³⁸

However, some of these initiatives do not appear to have been introduced with the NITI Aayog Responsible AI series' systems and societal considerations in mind. Ahmedabad, a city in Gujarat, for instance, is using AI-based video surveillance to "monitor and address various issues beyond its abilities, such as tracking traffic violations or unidentified activities"³⁹, a development with significant implications for civil liberties and human rights in the city and beyond. Uttar Pradesh is using AI-aided video analysis to monitor prisoners, and Tamil Nadu is using facial recognition to track student attendance and truancy rates.⁴⁰

³⁵ 'Grievances Redressal,' Unique Identification Authority of India, https://uidai.gov.in/en/?option=com_content&view=article&id=57&Itemid=105.

³⁶ 'UIDAI partners with indigenous GenAI Company Sarvam AI to enhance user experience of Aadhaar services,' Government of India Press Information Bureau, 18 March 2025, <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2112485>.

³⁷ 'Six notable Indian state governments AI initiatives in 2024,' IndiaAI, 10 November 2024, <https://indiaai.gov.in/article/six-notable-indian-state-governments-ai-initiatives-in-2024>.

³⁸ 'Artificial intelligence to advise farmers on pests and diseases in crops,' IndiaAI, 18 August 2020, <https://indiaai.gov.in/case-study/artificial-intelligence-to-advise-farmers-on-pests-and-diseases-in-crops>.

³⁹ 'Ahmedabad becomes the first Indian city to get an AI-linked surveillance system,' IndiaAI, January 11, 2024, <https://indiaai.gov.in/news/ahmedabad-becomes-the-first-indian-city-to-get-an-ai-linked-surveillance-system>.

⁴⁰ 'How the Indian Government is Championing the AI Revolution,' Analytics India Magazine, August 2020, <https://analyticsindiamag.com/ai-features/use-cases-of-ai-in-indian-government-a-comprehensive-report-by-aimresearch/>.

Approach to AI standardisation

Main features of the standardisation system

The Indian Standards Institution (ISI) was a founding member of ISO in 1946 and the only member at the time which represented a “country that corresponded more or less to the definition of a ‘developing’ country”.⁴¹ The ISI was replaced by the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS), India’s national standards body, which today develops and publishes standards across all major sectors and is also responsible for implementing conformity assessment schemes. BIS sits within the Indian government’s Ministry of Consumer Affairs.

In addition to BIS, 12 government agencies and some private sector organisations contribute to standards development in India. However, only standards recognised by BIS are considered “indigenous” (domestically developed) Indian Standards.

While Indian Standards are generally voluntary, the Government of India can select products for mandatory compliance with relevant Indian standards out of concern for public health and safety or national security.

National AI-focused standardisation initiatives

The Government of India has recognised the importance of standardisation as a tool for facilitating AI adoption. TRAI’s recommendations for AI in telecommunications, for instance, reflect the ministry’s substantial attention to developments in AI standardisation.⁴² MEITY Committee A’s report specifically observes that improved data and metadata standards, including data security and fairness standards, will facilitate the sharing of high-quality data in a privacy-sensitive and unbiased manner.⁴³ NITI Aayog’s Responsible AI series points frequently to standards as flexible, innovation-

⁴¹ ‘Friendship Among Equals’ (International Standards Organisation, 1997), 51, https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/about%20ISO/docs/en/Friendship_among_equals.pdf.

⁴² ‘Leveraging Artificial Intelligence and Big Data in Telecommunication Sector’.

⁴³ ‘Report of Committee A on Platforms and Data in Artificial Intelligence’, 11–12, 15.

enabling tools for governance, citing challenges in designing regulations that can keep up with the pace of technological developments in AI.⁴⁴

Indian standards organisations have also demonstrated keen interest in AI standards. BIS, in its 2019 Standards National Action Plan, highlighted AI as a key area for future standards work.⁴⁵ Both BIS and the Department of Telecommunications (DOT) have established standardisation committees with a core focus on AI. The BIS Artificial Intelligence subcommittee is composed of more than 30 expert representatives from government, academia, and industry working across nine key areas,⁴⁶ while the DOT's subcommittee is examining the role AI can play in improving 5G coverage and connectivity across India.⁴⁷ Furthermore, the IndiaAI platform is tracking the government's development of data and metadata standards.⁴⁸

Engagement in international standardisation

BIS represents India in ISO and IEC, and is a participating member of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42. While BIS has yet to draft or publish any indigenous AI standards, it has adopted at least 19 AI-related ISO/IEC standards as Indian Standards, indicating active engagement and monitoring of developments at the international level.⁴⁹

⁴⁴ 'Responsible AI #AIFORALL: Approach Document for India Part 1—Principles for Responsible AI'; 'Responsible AI #AIFORALL: Approach Document for India Part 2—Operationalizing Principles for Responsible AI' (NITI Aayog, August 2021), <https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2021-08/Part2-Responsible-AI-12082021.pdf>.

⁴⁵ 'Standards National Action Plan' (Bureau of Indian Standards, 2019), <https://www.bis.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/SNAP-Documents.pdf>.

⁴⁶ 'Program of Work: Electronics and Information Technology Department', n.d., https://www.services.bis.gov.in/php/BIS_2.0/bisconnect/pow_details?tecd=66, https://tsdsi.in/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Report-ml_v3.4-20191213-1.pdf; 'LITD 30—Artificial Intelligence Sectional Committee Composition', n.d., https://www.services.bis.gov.in/php/BIS_2.0/bisconnect/dgdashboard/committee_sso/composition/386/2; 'Working Group Details', n.d., https://www.services.bis.gov.in/php/BIS_2.0/bisconnect/dgdashboard/committee_sso/workingGroupDetails/386.

⁴⁷ 'Report on Machine Learning in Future Networks & Role of Standardization Workshop' (Telecommunications Standards Development Society, India, 12 December 2019), https://tsdsi.in/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Report-ml_v3.4-20191213-1.pdf.

⁴⁸ 'Metadata and Data Standards,' IndiaAI Mission, <https://indiaai.gov.in/metadata-data-standards>.

⁴⁹ Search for 'artificial intelligence' at this link: https://standardsbis.bsbedge.com/BIS_SearchStandard.aspx?keyword=artificial%20intelligence&id=0.

